

EMPLACING ARCHITECTURAL EDUCATION IN A SOCIOPHYSICAL TERRITORY

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INTRODUCTION

Placemaking can contribute to create learning places that are integrated into the community, rather than confined to the classroom. Moreover, the combination of placemaking with artistic practices offers an opportunity to integrate educational activities into the cultural, social and physical milieu. In the collaborative reflective processes which placemaking conveys, artists and educational staff, students and residents all become knowledge providers through learning processes embedded in a sociophysical territory.

One of the purposes of the A-Place project "Linking places through networked artistic practices",¹ co-funded by the Creative Europe 2019-2023 programme, is to create transversal learning spaces with placemaking activities that link artistic practices with educational programmes at different levels, from high school to higher education. Since October 2019, we have been carrying out in L'Hospitalet de Llobregat, a city which is part of the metropolitan area of Barcelona, Spain, a comprehensive programme of learning activities integrated in the community. The purpose of these activities was to involve students and staff from university and high schools, artists and neighbours, in a common reflection on the sense of place and the collective identity. The activities included mapping of the sociophysical territory carried out onsite –pedagogic activities in public spaces and public facilities, urban walks with neighbours representing diverse social groups– and online –with digital maps and through social media–, and joint teaching and learning activities with high-school pupils and architecture students to identify meanings associated to places and represent them with texts, images, videos and installations in public spaces.

Creating places and designing spaces

The idea of place –in opposition to the concept of space– implies the existence of bonds between people and the environment they inhabit. Place is commonly referred to as space with meaning, as a “field or care” as Tuan described it.² For Sime “The term 'place', as opposed to space, implies a strong emotional tie, temporary or more long-lasting, between a person and a particular physical location”.³ Place is then opposed to abstract, geometric space. Unlike a space considered as a blank slate or empty container, a place is never empty. As Relph argued, places are “centres of meaning, or focuses of intention and purpose”,⁴ meanings and functions which are not the same for all individuals or groups.

People use public spaces, although they live in places; they create places by endowing spaces with value. However, architects have been often criticized for being more concerned with designing spaces

than with creating places, with the formal and material characteristics of the spaces than with the people who will live in them; in short, more with abstract space than with lived space. As early as the 1970s, Tuan called on design professionals not to reduce the complexity of being-in-the-world to simple abstractions,⁵ a person into a component of a functional mechanism, either the building or the city. Rather, he appealed to planners and designers to expand their discourses in order to bridge the gap between the abstract world of design and the world of experience.⁶ This dilemma between abstract space and lived space was also echoed in by Norberg-Schulz's *Genius loci*.⁷ However, there are still discussions on how to overcome this dilemma in professional practice and education. Tonkiss, for instance, contends that cities are "material realities which also take their shape in memory and perception"⁸ and for Yaneva social and physical structures are indivisible elements of a unique construction process: "We should question the assumption that casts social factors as the cause, while architecture is reduced to playing the effect".⁹

Placemaking process: a learning place

The term "placemaking" has been used since the 1990s by the non-profit organisation Project for Public Spaces, which has subsequently defined it in the following terms: "Placemaking is both a philosophy and a practical process for transforming public spaces. It is centered on observing, listening to, and asking questions of the people who live, work, and play in a particular space in order to understand their needs and aspirations for that space and for their community as a whole".¹⁰ According to PPS, "successful" places have four qualities: "they are accessible; people are engaged in activities there; the space is comfortable and has a good image; and finally, it is a sociable place",¹¹ and placemaking is "a collaborative process by which we can shape our public realm in order to maximize shared value".¹²

Place and placemaking are hardly distinguishable if we think of a place as a social construction. In vernacular culture, such a distinction does not arise: place is already placemaking. But the links between people and places, once taken for granted, have been broken and need to be reinstated. Thus, it is argued that public spaces no longer reflect people's lives and aspirations, so they need to be "transformed". But people cannot re-establish lost links on their own, and this is where placemaking – as a process guided by placemaking experts – comes in to help. In fact, such self-consciousness about the act of "placemaking" is evidence of a loss, of a crisis derived from our expert culture; as Alexander claimed, a state of "selfconsciousness" which emerged with modern architecture.¹³

To the extent that placemaking aims to empower people to transform their living environment into a "place to feel good in, to belong to and be proud of"¹⁴ it can be seen as an educational process structured in a sequence of stages: defining a place and identifying stakeholders, evaluating existing environments, proposing a vision for change, implementing and evaluating the changes, assessing the impact of the transformations and propose new actions.¹⁵ This sequence is not linear, but iterative: once the change has been performed, a new process of action and reflection follows, leading to a reformulation of the aims and to further actions.¹⁶ As in action research, those participants affected by the problem at stake are involved "in the research through a cyclical process of fact finding, action, and reflection, leading to further inquiry and action for change",¹⁷ as described by Minkler. Therefore, we can think of placemaking as a "learning place" embodied in the sociophysical milieu and as participatory action research where stakeholders are involved in the definition and solution of a problem, with the shared purpose of transforming an existing reality.

Placemaking and the architect's education

Today, it is widely acknowledged that the creation of liveable and sustainable environments requires the participation of experts and non-experts. As stated in the New Urban Agenda published in 2017, it is necessary to "promote civic engagement, engender a sense of belonging and ownership among all

their inhabitants [...] enhance social and intergenerational interactions, cultural expressions and political participation [...] and foster social cohesion, inclusion and safety in peaceful and pluralistic societies, where the needs of all inhabitants are met”.¹⁸ In a context that seeks to promote participation, architects become one more actor –and not necessarily the most privileged one– in a collective endeavour aimed at addressing societal and environmental problems.¹⁹

Schneekloth and Shibley see placemaking as an opportunity to “move beyond expert models to relocate and embed architecture –*implace* it– within a broader human endeavor that we call placemaking”.²⁰ In placemaking, “knowledges of the professional, the place, and the local people are shared, disputed, negotiated, and considered”.²¹ As Till argued, in order to work with non-experts, architects might need “to re-imagine their knowledge from the perspective of the user”²² in order “to move between the world of expert and user, with one set of knowledge and experience informing the other”.²³ Thus, placemaking enables the creation of spaces of dialogue between experts and non-experts; it is an opportunity to expand the architecture discourse beyond the realm of the expert culture onto the complexity of real problems and enabling people to take part in the “inclusive, democratic, and civic projects of the twenty-first century”,²⁴ as Schneekloth and Shibley contended.

Through placemaking activities, in A-Place we have created learning places which overcome the boundaries between academia and community, art and architecture, digital and physical spaces. These learning places can foster a form of situated knowledge production involving experts and non-experts, which could contribute to facilitate future professionals a better understanding of the issues which concern people and the skills to effectively incorporate them in the design practices; that is, to engage learners in practices aimed at interlinking “different cultural codes, experiences and languages”,²⁵ as Giroux intended.

A WEAVED PLACE

In the past, the territory of the city L’Hospitalet de Llobregat was an agricultural area located between a mountain range, the Llobregat river and the sea, at the southwest of Barcelona. It received the status of city in 1925, and soon started to attract industries and then migrants from other regions of Spain, especially between 1960 and 1980, until it became the second largest city of Catalonia, with a population of around 265,000.²⁶ As a result of its development, the city is now part of the urban continuum of the metropolitan area of Barcelona, to the point that it is hard to distinguish where one city ends and the other begins, unless we look the municipal boundaries in a map. In the last decades, a new wave of migration coming from other countries, especially outside Europe, has replaced the earlier generations of migrants. Over the years, the city has grown as an aggregation of urban fragments which have filled a territory criss-crossed by transport infrastructures, train lines and motorways. Today, it is a multicultural society with 28% of the population born abroad, around 50,000 of them from non-EU countries. Some of its neighbourhoods have one of the highest densities in Europe (53,119 inhabitants/km² in 2011).²⁷ To avoid segregation and social exclusion among groups from multiple backgrounds living in dense and separated urban environments, the city is particularly committed to developing a sense of identity that brings together diverse social groups and neighbourhoods and reinforces their sense of belonging.

As part of the activities of the A-Place project, in October 2019 we started the programme “A Weaved Place” with the purpose of involving community actors and architecture students in activities aimed at forging links across the multiple layers of the sociophysical territory of L’Hospitalet (Figure 1): mapping abandoned and ignored spaces in neighbourhoods, finding out the memories and stories that people associate with places, and proposing interventions to activate the identified places. Due to the lockdown undergone in Spain during the spring of 2020, some of the activities were carried out entirely online, and later in blended format. These included:

- Mapping of the sociophysical territory carried out onsite and online (urban walks, digital maps) with diverse media (texts, photographs, videos)
- Pedagogic activities in public spaces, public facilities and online environments
- Interventions in public space (designing and building objects)

Figure 1. Interlinking the layers of the sociophysical territory with community-based learning and creative activities.

Creating transversal learning spaces

In architectural education, project-based methodologies have been used to integrate the various curricular areas, for example, design, construction, and urban planning, in the design studio. In this transversal learning space, faculty from the different subject areas interact with each other and students are expected to bring together the knowledge acquired in the various courses. Altogether, students and faculty reproduce in the design studio a model of reality “while also acting as a cohesive devise that builds community amongst the students and staff”,²⁸ as Brown asserted. Furthermore, with “live” and “real” projects design studio education is extended beyond the academic premises –in the physical and conceptual sense– to create links with “real” problems which need to be solved interacting with “real” community actors in “real” settings.

However, as Luckan contends, “The fundamental problem is that interdisciplinary curriculum does not necessarily translate into interdisciplinary practice” which can only occur when architects “engage with the culture of place”.²⁹ Learning places created around placemaking enable to move beyond the interdisciplinarity of the design studio, and to transcend the interlinking between architectural curriculum and practice. Since placemaking aims to create “good” and “successful” places in collaboration with other community actors, architects –as students and as professionals– need to engage in a research in and with the community. This research embraces not only architectural and urban issues, but also ethnographic, sociological, cultural and political ones as well. This means, as Schneekloth and Shibley argued, to emplace architecture to make it part of “a larger practice of place”.³⁰

In order to emplace our learning in L’Hospitalet, during the academic year 2020-21 we created a transversal learning space which included three subjects of our five-year architectural curriculum (Figure 2): LAB Design Unit (fourth year), Urbanism (fourth year) and Systems of Representation (third year). According to a tripartite structure based on the sequence Mapping-Building-Reflecting (Figure 3), each subject would contribute to the common task of finding spaces in the city to be activated through placemaking interventions: urbanism students made an analysis of the urban structure and identified potential spots for the intervention (Figure 4); students in the representation course contacted social and cultural organizations, activist groups and civic leaders and organize meetings and forum discussions online during the lockdown (Figure 5), and later made a visual analysis of the cityscape with photographs (Figure 6), and design studio students made proposals for mobile structures to hold performances, exhibitions and workshops in public spaces (Figure 7). Through the interconnection of different subjects and the contact with communities, students were expected to develop their capacities for interdisciplinary work and their communication skills with non-experts. For the community members, participation in the activities would contribute to increasing individuals' and groups' awareness of the value and meanings they give to their living environment, and to sharing these with the community. For both academic and community stakeholders, their participation in the activities would lead to a reciprocal exchange of knowledge.

Figure 2. Emplacing architectural education in the community.

Figure 3. Interlinking the three subjects of the curriculum in project-based learning.

Figure 4. Proposal for a space to be activated with placemaking activities. Students: Lucas Escudero, Jordi Carbajo, Virginia Muñoz, and Ekaterina Smal.

Figure 5. Focus group with community representatives held online. Students: Guillem Hernández, Diego Lahoz, and Olav Haugen, Systems of Representation, 2019-20.

Mapping places

Soulless City
Forgotten Spaces

"Son lugares aparentemente olvidados donde parece predominar la memoria del pasado sobre el presente."

Solà-Morales

"They are its margins, lacking any effective incorporation; they are interior islands voided of activity; they are forgotten, oversights and leftovers which have remained outside the urban oversights and leftovers which have remained outside the urban dynamic."

Solà-Morales

"these are places that are foreign to the urban system, mentally exterior in the physical interior of the city, appearing as its negative image"

Solà-Morales

"Nosotros incluimos en la noción de lugar antropológico la posibilidad de los recorridos que en él se efectúan, los discursos que allí se sostienen y el lenguaje que lo caracteriza."

Augé

Figure 6. Visual analysis of the city, linked to readings on urban theory. Student: Melissa Gandara, Systems of Representation 2021-22.

Figure 7. Prototype of modular structure to install in public spaces. Students: Omar Masoud, Ernest Sánchez, and Carolina Soto, LAB Design Unit, 2020-21.

Creating learning places

Figure 8. Sequence mapping, reflecting, building.

From April to October 2021, the interlinking of activities was extended beyond the limits of the academic curriculum to include community actors –neighbours, students and teachers from local schools– in learning activities and interventions taking place in the city premises, educational institutions and public spaces (Figure 8). We designed learning activities for high school students from local secondary schools to develop an awareness about the personal links they create with public spaces. The first task was to identify a place in the neighbourhood to which pupils attached a particular value, a life experience they had in the past, positive, negative or neutral. They described the experience with a text and a photograph published in the online environment A-Place: MAPPING.³¹ After reading the accounts of the pupils and visiting the places they identified, architecture students made a proposal for an installation inspired in their experiences with places. Then, architecture students presented their proposals to the younger students in a joint event held in a square in front of the civic centre. The feedback and comments of the pupils were taken into consideration in the next design iteration. Finally, a prototype of the proposed intervention was built in the university campus, before it was installed in the public spaces of the neighbourhood, collaboratively by architecture students and pupils from secondary schools (Figure 9).

Figure 9. Installations in public space of the Bellvitge neighbourhood, L'Hospitalet, November 2020. Students (left to right, top to bottom): Mateo Juncos, Robert Martí, and Pau Martín; Nora Slenes Nilsen, Clàudia Pérez, and Dmytro Zhechev; Inês de Oliveira, Juliana Díaz, and Leonardo Fiore; Duygo Demiroğlu, Ivette Gutiérrez, Isabella Jaramillo, and Lexian Ye.

The activities were regularly disseminated through the A-Place social media channels,³² and the installation in the public space was followed by the local media, press and television.³³ This was important for students to exercise their communication skills, explaining in a non-expert language the work they did for the local media, television and newspapers.

With the combined activities we aimed at promoting an interdisciplinary curriculum, to increase students' awareness of the often invisible meanings that underlie public space, to contribute to develop their communication skills to work with non-experts. Moreover, these activities open up other learning possibilities for students: to understand the role of representation tools in the understanding of a city (drawings, photographs); to approach the notion of place from different conceptual perspectives; to actually transform a public space, with ephemeral interventions planned and implemented with community members. This learning space situated in the community, engaging various disciplines and levels of education, can be seen as a case of transdisciplinary knowledge acquisition in architectural education.³⁴

Figure 10. Dissemination of the interventions in public space through local media.

CONCLUSION

To implement learning process embedded in the community we need flexible strategies to manage open, creative process over time. Dealing with constraints and overcoming unexpected obstacles, are part of this process. Moreover, interconnecting subjects in the curriculum, creating links between universities and high schools, and fostering fruitful dialogues between experts and non-experts in a specific social and physical context, all require an extraordinary communication effort from all involved: staff, students and community actors. It is also necessary for all participants involved to understand and to situate themselves in an open, dynamic and collaborative learning process. This also requires a continuous communication among all actors involved in the learning process, which is key to maintaining the level of commitment of all involved.

The ultimate purpose of the transversal, community-embedded learning activities we designed and implemented is to bring about structural changes both in the academic curriculum and in the sociophysical territory. However, such changes might take a long time and they are difficult to trace. From a community perspective, a placemaking can contribute to visualize meanings, values and experiences that underlie the physical space through educational and participatory creative activities. The extent to which changes contribute to increase the sense of belonging and identity of the community members is however difficult to determine, particularly in the short-term. Similarly, a lasting transformation of the academic curriculum resulting from transversal learning experiences carried out under specific conditions (limited time, actors involved, results obtained) could be difficult to achieve.

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NOTES

- ¹ <https://www.a-place.eu/>, accessed October 18, 2022.
- ² Yi-Fu Tuan "Space and place: humanistic perspective", in *Philosophy in geography*, pp. 387-427. (Dordrecht: Springer, 1979), 417.
- ³ Jonathan D. Sime, "Creating places or designing spaces?" *Journal of Environmental Psychology* 6, no. 1 (1986): 50.
- ⁴ Edward Relph. *Place and placelessness* (London: Pion, 1976), 22.
- ⁵ Yi-Fu Tuan. *Space and place: The perspective of experience* (University of Minnesota Press, 1977), 202.
- ⁶ Leandro Madrazo, "The Social Construction of a Neighbourhood Identity", *Open House International* (2019): 77.
- ⁷ Christian Norberg-Schulz, *Genius loci: Towards a phenomenology of architecture* (New York: Rizzoli, 1979), 11.
- ⁸ Fran Tonkiss, *Space, the city and social theory: Social relations and urban forms* (Polity, 2005), 2.
- ⁹ Albená Yaneva, *Mapping controversies in architecture* (Routledge, 2016), 33.
- ¹⁰ Project for Public Spaces, accessed October 18, 2022, <https://www.pps.org/article/5-steps-to-making-places>
- ¹¹ Project for Public Spaces, accessed October 18, 2022, <https://www.pps.org/article/grplacefeat>
- ¹² Project for Public Spaces, accessed October 18, 2022, <https://www.pps.org/category/placemaking>
- ¹³ Christopher Alexander, *Notes on the Synthesis of Form* (Harvard University Press, 1964), 32.
- ¹⁴ The empty square, accessed October 18, 2022, <https://www.theemptysquare.org/stories/placemaking-education#:~:text=Placemaking%20is%20an%20inclusive%20and,in%20and%20where%20humans%20thrive>
- ¹⁵ Project for Public Spaces, accessed October 18, 2022, <https://www.pps.org/article/5-steps-to-making-places>
- ¹⁶ Ortrun Zuber-Skerritt, "Action learning and action research: paradigm, praxis and programs", *Effective change management through action research and action learning: Concepts, perspectives, processes and applications* 1, no. 20 (2001): 1-27.
- ¹⁷ Meredith Minkler, "Using participatory action research to build healthy communities", *Public health reports* 115, no. 2-3 (2000): 191.
- ¹⁸ New Urban Agenda- Habitat III, accessed October 18, 2022, <https://habitat3.org/wp-content/uploads/NUA-English.pdf>
- ¹⁹ Ashraf M. Salama, "A theory for integrating knowledge in architectural design education", *ArchNet-IJAR: International Journal of Architectural Research* 2, no. 1 (2008): 100-128.
- ²⁰ Lynda H. Schneekloth and Robert G. Shibley, "Implacing architecture into the practice of placemaking", *Journal of Architectural Education* 53, no. 3 (2000): 131.
- ²¹ Schneekloth and Shibley, "Implacing architecture into the practice of placemaking", (2000): 136.
- ²² Jeremy Till, "The negotiation of hope", in *Architecture and participation*, ed. Peter Blundell Jones, Doina Petrescu, and Jeremy Till (Routledge, 2013), 31.
- ²³ Till, "The negotiation of hope", (Routledge, 2013), 33.
- ²⁴ Schneekloth and Shibley, "Implacing architecture into the practice of placemaking", (2000): 131.
- ²⁵ Henry A. Giroux, *Border Pedagogy in the Age of Postmodernism* (Routledge, 1973).
- ²⁶ City Population, accessed October 18, 2022, https://www.citypopulation.de/en/spain/cataluna/barcelona/08101_lhospitalet_de_llobregat/
- ²⁷ Eurostat, accessed October 18, 2022, <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/products-eurostat-news/-/ddn-20200430-1>
- ²⁸ James Benedict Brown, *A critique of the live project*, PhD diss (Queen's University Belfast, 2012), 33.
- ²⁹ Yashaen Luckan, "The transformation of architectural education towards establishing architecture as responsive, relevant and ethical social practice" (paper presented at the UIA Conference in Durban, South Africa, August 2014), accessed October 18, 2022, https://www.academia.edu/14870812/the_transformation_of_architectural_education_towards_establishing_architecture_as_responsive_relevant_and_ethical_social_practice_published_in_the_conference_proceedings_of_the_UIA_Conference_in_Durban_South_Africa_August_2014
- ³⁰ Schneekloth and Shibley, "Implacing architecture into the practice of placemaking", (2000): 133.
- ³¹ See A-Place: MAPPING, accessed May 30, 2022, <https://www.a-place.eu/en/mapping?actions=%5B%22%23aplacemappingLH%22%5D&cities=%5B%5D&concepts=%5B%5D&evaluations=%5B%5D&interventions=%5B%5D#map>
- ³² See Facebook, accessed October 18, 2022, <https://fb.watch/dj1olkKEtQ/>; Instagram, accessed October 18, 2022, https://www.instagram.com/p/COAhILsdKH/?utm_source=ig_web_copy_link

³³ Reportage on local television, accessed October 18, 2022, <https://lhdigital.cat/web/digital-h/veure-multimedia?xarxald=618be0d2336e6611bcf3d48a&vimeoid=undefined&video=&titol=Joves%20de%20Bellvitge%20embelleixen%20la%20pla%C3%A7a%20de%20la%20Cultura>

³⁴ Salama, "A theory for integrating knowledge", (2008): 100-128.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Agnew, John A. *Place and politics: The geographical mediation of state and society*. Routledge, 2014.

Appleyard, Donald. "Livable streets: protected neighborhoods?." *The ANNALS of the American Academy of Political and Social Science* 451, no. 1 (1980): 106-117.

Casey, Edward. *The fate of place: A philosophical history*. University of California Press, 2013.

Cilliers, Elizelle J. and Wim Timmermans. "The importance of creative participatory planning in the public place-making process". *Environment and Planning B: Planning and Design*, 41(3) (2014): 413-429.

Courage, Cara, and Anita McKeown. *Creative Placemaking*. Routledge, 2019.

Hes, Dominique, and Cristina Hernandez-Santin, eds. *Placemaking fundamentals for the built environment*. Singapore: Palgrave Macmillan, 2020.

Johnson, Amanda J. and Troy D. Glover. "Understanding urban public space in a leisure context." *Leisure Sciences*, 35(2) (2013): 190-197.

Lydon, Mike, and Anthony Garcia. "A tactical urbanism how-to." In *Tactical urbanism*, pp. 171-208. Island Press, Washington, DC, 2015.

Massey, Doreen. "A global sense of place." In *The cultural geography reader*, pp. 269-275. Routledge, 2008.

Toolis, Erin E. "Theorizing critical placemaking as a tool for reclaiming public space." *American Journal of Community Psychology* 59, no. 1-2 (2017): 184-199.